

EFFECTIVENESS OF PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN COOPERATIVE AND NON-COOPERATIVE DAIRIES – A STUDY IN KARNATAKA STATE

S.ARUN KUMAR

Assistant Professor, PES University, Bangalore.

Dr. S.JAMBULINGAM

Associate Professor, Department of Business Administration, Annamalai University, Chidambaram, TN.

Abstract

Performance Management System (PMS) is a combination of planning, management and appraisal of both performance results and competency behavior. This study undergone the perceptions of cooperative and non-cooperative dairy farm employees about effectiveness of PMS with reference to results, inputs, time, focus, quality, cost and output on career and personal growth of the employees par excellence along with focusing on effectiveness of PMS on organization performance. For this purpose Karnataka Co-Operative Milk Producer's Federation Limited (KMF) of cooperative and Srikrishna Dairy Private Limited of non-cooperative dairies from Karnataka state were selected for this study and 250 employees from each were considered as sample. A comparative analysis on effectiveness of performance management system in cooperative and non-cooperative dairies revealed that there is a significant difference found between cooperative and non-cooperative dairies towards effectiveness of PMS with reference to results and output, where non-cooperative dairy are found better than cooperative dairies. With reference to input, focus, quality and output of PMS in cooperative and non-cooperative dairies shows that there is no significant difference. Whereas, with reference to time of PMS in cooperative and non-cooperative dairies there is a significant difference found between these two dairy industries, where the non-cooperative dairy employees are more positive in this regard than their counterpart cooperative dairy employees. Hence, the satisfaction levels of employees towards current PMS in cooperative and non-cooperative dairies indicate significant because the Non-Cooperative dairy employees found higher satisfaction than the employees of Cooperative dairy.

Keywords: Effectiveness, Performance Management System, Cooperative and Non-cooperative dairies.

INTRODUCTION

Performance Management System (PMS) is a combination of planning, management and appraisal of both performance results and competency behavior. PMS is considered as the core for people management process in form at their peak level, the organization can succeed their goals and compete. This study undergone the perceptions of cooperative and non-cooperative dairy farm employees about effectiveness of PMS and focuses the career and personal growth, communication between employees and their superiors, recognizing and rewarding the employees par excellence along with focusing on effectiveness of PMS on organization performance. Thus, effective performance management is essential to businesses through both formal and informal processes or cooperative and non-cooperative organisations. This helps the organisation to align their employees, resources, and systems to meet their strategic objectives. It works as a dashboard too, providing an early warning of potential problems and

allowing managers to know when they must make adjustments to keep a business on track. In the best PMS, the entire organization operates from a single, verified version of the truth, and all employees understand both the organization's overall performance and how they contributed to it. At the end of every shift at one company in the dairy sector, all employees pass the daily production board, where they can see their department's results and the impact on the plant's performance. The company has linked the top-line financial metrics that shareholders and the board of directors care about to the production metrics that matter on the ground. Frontline employees can see the thread that connects their daily performance with the performance of their plant and business units. Therefore, this study seeks to identify employee perceptions over various aspects of PMS followed by the selected two dairies of cooperative and non-cooperative and find out the satisfaction levels on the current PMS in the study organisations. Hence, the present study is much significance as research findings of this study will help policy makers especially those of HRM managers of cooperative and non-cooperative sector units, especially the Dairy Industry, to adopt more realistic policies regarding the PMS.

Today is the era of knowledge work and knowledge workers, in which work is information-based and mental activity, and people construct their work routines in response to fluid, changing requirements. Human resource management relies heavily on PMSs, which contribute to corporate strategy. Through these systems, businesses stress their strategic direction, ensure accountability, create value for their customers, and eventually generate profits. As the amount of financial and non-financial resources invested in PMS is enormous, it is crucial that these systems are owned and utilised efficiently by all parties involved. In addition, businesses use PMS to motivate and retain their most valuable assets, their employees.

A well-designed PMS is absolutely necessary in a company like the dairy business, which is eager to expand daily. The dairy business is in dire need of strategic HR strategies at this level of globalisation. In this way, performance management aids in surviving internal rivalry within the company. Performance management is crucial for coordinating the different key organisational functions in this sector in order to achieve organisational objectives. Performance management also entails the development, execution, assessment, and evaluation of numerous processes that aid in tracking employee performance and promoting individual and organisational growth. To have a good management system that may enable employees to give a better performance for organisational development, performance management also aids in the distribution of job duties and performance improvement. Hence, in the present scenario, a research work on performance management of organisations producing dairy products is very much needed and a comparative study on co-operative and non-co-operative dairies is very much significant to analyse the effectiveness of performance managements systems becomes necessary.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Sajid Hussain Awan, et al. (2020) in their study on effectiveness of PMS for employee performance through engagement seeks to explore the effectiveness of a comprehensive PMS

in terms of employee performance. In this study the authors found that effectiveness of PMS determined by the extent of its accuracy and fairness, as recommended by previous researchers. The results indicated a significant impact of PMS and work engagement on task and contextual performance of employees. Teeroovengadam et al. (2019) investigate effectiveness of PMS from three types of organizational purposes, i.e. strategic, development and administrative. Similarly, in another study by Lappalainen et al. (2019) indicates effectiveness of PMS serves two main functions, i.e. judgmental and developmental, where the first one is evaluative and helps make administrative decisions about employees, whereas the developmental part is related to its potential for high performance. In another study done by Annette (2018) the independent variable is the PMS and the dependent variable is team effectiveness, indicating that team effectiveness is an essential outcome of deploying a PMS. The study reveals an efficient PMS can contribute to the effectiveness of a team spirit. McDonough (2015) studied on seven factors of effective team performance and observed that the proper and effective application of a PMS can produce functional outcome of team effectiveness. In another study done by Grobler, et al. (2006) defined performance management is a whole quality management programme that requires the use of all management instruments including performance evaluation to assure the attainment of performance objectives. The results indicate effective performance management will enable task coordination and execution. Eul-Kyoo Bae (2006) studied on major elements and issues in PMS, where the author aimed to explore and evaluate significant features and issues in PMS through a comprehensive literature analysis, as well as to provide guidelines for creating and implementing an effective PMS in businesses.

OBJECTIVES

1. To study the effectiveness of performance management system in cooperative and non-cooperative dairies with reference to results, inputs, time, focus, quality, cost and output.
2. To study the satisfaction levels of employees towards current performance management system in cooperative and non-cooperative dairies.
3. To perform comparative analysis of performance management system between cooperative and non-cooperative dairies

METHODOLOGY

Since, the main aim of this research is to study the performance management of organisations producing dairy products with reference cooperative and non-cooperative organisation in Karnataka state, the Karnataka Co-Operative Milk Producer's Federation Limited (KMF) of cooperative and Srikrishna Dairy Private Limited of non-cooperative are selected for this study. These two dairies collect milk from farmers, process the milk and sold in the market by their respective brands in the study area. Hence, these two dairies selected as the sample units for data collection. A purposive stratified random sampling method adopted for data collection from the employees of selected two dairies. As per the availability of data 594 employees are working in Nandini Dairy (cooperative) and 656 employees are working in Srikrishna Dairy under 4 categories of employment i.e. managers, supervisors, clerical and operational.

According to the Google Sample Calculation method 576 or more samples are needed to have a confidence level of 95% that the real value is within $\pm 3\%$ of the surveyed value. Hence, out of the total 1250 population (594 from Nandini Dairy and 656 from Srikrishna Dairy) 500 samples have been finalized for this study. Thus, 250 samples from Nandini Dairy and 250 samples from Srikrishna Dairy units were considered by random sampling method. These samples also categorically distributed under 4 grades of managers, supervisors, clerical staff and operational staff.

In this purpose a research tool was designed after a thorough review of earlier literature and finalised for data collection. With reference to effectiveness of performance management system there are seven areas in this tools which are: 1) results, 2) input, 3) time, 4) focus, 5) quality, 6) cost, and 7) output. For validity and reliability of the research tool Cronbach's alpha test was employed and found the standard value of reliability is 0.7 and results indicate that all the seven variables are indicating more than 0.7 Cronbach's alpha value. Therefore, the tool is proven reliable for research survey. For statistical process SPSS-18 was used to analyse the data by Univariate and multivariate analysis. The ANOVA test was undertaken for comparative analysis. Hence, the data analysis is presented in the following for more reliability of results.

DATA ANALYSIS

Table-1: Effectiveness of PMS with reference to Result in Dairy Industry of Karnataka State

SL. No	Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
1	I feel proud to be a part of this organization	41 (8.2)	53 (10.6)	108 (21.6)	128 (25.6)	170 (34.0)	500 (100.0)
2	My future growth opportunities look good in this organisation	53 (10.6)	83 (16.6)	99 (19.8)	110 (22.0)	155 (31.0)	500 (100.0)
3	The potentiality of the employees indicate the organisation growth	55 (11.0)	78 (15.6)	98 (19.6)	90 (18.0)	179 (35.8)	500 (100.0)
4	My company give adequate training to improve my professional skills	44 (8.8)	81 (16.2)	94 (18.8)	110 (22.0)	171 (34.2)	500 (100.0)
5	Management encourages new ideas and innovation at work place for the better output	52 (10.4)	78 (15.6)	91 (18.2)	107 (21.4)	172 (34.4)	500 (100.0)
6	There is clear understanding of the future direction for the benefit of the company	65 (13.0)	79 (15.8)	95 (19.0)	114 (22.8)	147 (29.4)	500 (100.0)

Source: Survey data.

The Table-1 presents the effectiveness of PMS with reference to result and output in Dairy Industry of Karnataka State. It is found that a predominated group of 34.0 percent is strongly agreed, 25.6 percent are agreed, 21.6 percent are neutral, 10.6 percent are disagreed and 8.2 percent are strongly disagreed that they feel proud to be a part of this organisation, 31.0 percent are strongly agreed, 22.0 percent are agreed, 19.8 percent are neutral, 16.6 percent are disagreed and 10.6 percent are strongly disagreed that their future growth opportunities look good in this organisation. The data shows that 35.8 percent are strongly agreed, 18.0 percent are agreed, 19.6 percent are neutral, 15.6 percent are disagreed and 11.0 percent are strongly disagreed

about the potentiality of the employees indicate the organisation growth. It is noticed from the data 34.2 percent are strongly agreed, 22.0 percent are agreed, 18.8 percent are neutral 16.2 percent are disagreed and 8.8 percent are strongly disagreed about their company that gives adequate training to improve their professional skills, 34.4 percent are strongly agreed, 21.4 percent are agreed, 18.2 percent are neutral, 15.6 percent are disagreed and 10.4 percent are strongly disagreed that their management encourages new ideas and innovation at work place for the better output, 29.4 percent are strongly agreed, 22.8 percent are agreed, 19.0 percent are neutral, 15.8 percent are disagreed and 13.0 percent are strongly disagreed that there is clear understanding of the future direction for the benefit of the company.

Table-2: Effectiveness of PMS with reference to Inputs in Dairy Industry of Karnataka State

SL. No	Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
1	I have performance standards in work ability	62 (12.4)	72 (14.4)	105 (21.0)	120 (24.0)	141 (28.2)	500 (100.0)
2	PMS helps to improve skills among employees	53 (10.6)	75 (15.0)	85 (17.0)	121 (24.2)	166 (33.2)	500 (100.0)
3	My company recognizes and honors for better performance	55 (10.2)	83 (16.6)	107 (21.4)	121 (24.2)	134 (26.8)	500 (100.0)
4	Employees are rewarded in time for excellence in performance and achievement of results	51 (10.2)	79 (15.8)	99 (19.8)	121 (24.2)	150 (30.0)	500 (100.0)
5	The company encourages job rotation as a development tool of more productivity	47 (9.4)	67 (13.4)	110 (22.0)	113 (22.6)	163 (32.6)	500 (100.0)

Source: Survey data.

Table-2 discusses the effectiveness of PMS with reference to inputs in dairy industry of Karnataka State. It is observed that out of total respondents 28.2 percent are strongly agreed, 24.0 percent are agreed, 21.0 percent are neutral, 14.4 percent are disagreed and 12.4 percent are strongly disagreed that they have performance standards in work ability, 33.2 percent are strongly agreed, 24.2 percent are agreed, 17.0 percent are neutral, 15.0 percent are disagreed and 10.6 percent are strongly disagreed that PMS helps to improve skills among employees. The data reveals that 26.8 percent are strongly agreed, 24.2 percent are agreed, 21.4 percent are neutral, 16.6 percent are disagreed and 10.2 percent are strongly disagreed that their company recognizes and honors for better performance, 30.0 percent are strongly agreed, 24.2 percent are agreed, 19.8 percent are neutral, 15.8 percent are disagreed and 10.2 percent are strongly disagreed that the employees are rewarded in time for excellence in performance and achievement of results. Finally it is noticed that 32.6 percent are strongly agreed, 22.6 percent are agreed, 22.0 percent are neutral, 13.4 percent are disagreed and 9.4 percent are strongly disagreed that their company encourages job rotation as a development tool of more productivity.

Table-3: Effectiveness of PMS with reference to Time in Dairy Industry of Karnataka State

SL. No	Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
1	This company is good for work at present scenario	55 (11.0)	71 (14.2)	95 (19.0)	104 (20.8)	175 (35.0)	500 (100.0)
2	I am always willing to put efforts for the development of this company	43 (8.6)	63 (12.6)	97 (19.4)	110 (22.0)	187 (37.4)	500 (100.0)
3	I would rate this company as amongst the most desirable companies to work	71 (14.2)	90 (18.0)	104 (20.8)	113 (22.6)	122 (24.4)	500 (100.0)
4	My job is secured in the company as long as I perform well	56 (11.2)	75 (15.0)	105 (21.0)	111 (22.2)	153 (30.6)	500 (100.0)
5	There are opportunities for everyone in this organization to learn and grow in different areas	55 (11.0)	75 (15.0)	88 (17.6)	125 (25.0)	157 (31.4)	500 (100.0)
6	I am able to achieve my career objectives in this company	56 (11.2)	76 (15.2)	97 (19.4)	116 (23.2)	155 (31.0)	500 (100.0)
7	The vision, mission and goals of this company are understood clearly	41 (8.2)	57 (11.4)	85 (17.0)	119 (23.8)	198 (39.6)	500 (100.0)
8	There is freedom to express my views even though they might contradict the views of my superiors	76 (15.2)	79 (15.8)	98 (19.6)	111 (22.2)	136 (27.2)	500 (100.0)

Source: Survey data.

Table-3 represents the effectiveness of PMS with reference to time in Dairy Industry of Karnataka State. The data reveals that a predominated group of 35.0 percent is strongly agreed, 20.8 percent are agreed, 19.0 percent are neutral, 14.2 percent are disagreed and 11.0 percent are strongly disagreed that their company is good for work at present scenario, 37.4 percent are strongly agreed, 22.0 percent are agreed, 19.4 percent are neutral, 12.6 percent are disagreed and 8.6 percent are strongly disagreed that they always willing to put efforts for the development of this company. Regarding to the data 24.4 percent are strongly agreed, 22.6 percent are agreed, 20.8 percent are neutral, 18.0 percent are disagreed and 14.2 percent are strongly disagreed that they would rate this company as amongst the most desirable companies to work, 30.6 percent are strongly agreed, 22.2 percent are agreed, 21.0 percent are neutral, 15.0 percent are disagreed and 11.2 percent are strongly disagreed that their job is secured in the company as long as they perform well. It is found that out of total respondents of 31.4 percent are strongly agreed, 25.0 percent are agreed, 17.6 percent are neutral, 15.0 percent are disagreed and 11.0 percent are strongly disagreed that there are opportunities for everyone in this organization to learn and grow in different areas, 31.0 percent are strongly agreed, 23.2 percent are agreed, 19.4 percent are neutral, 15.2 percent are disagreed and 11.2 percent are strongly disagreed that they are able to achieve their career objectives in this company. From the data 39.6 percent are strongly agreed, 23.8 percent are agreed, 17.0 percent are neutral, 11.4 percent are disagreed and 8.2 percent are strongly disagreed that their vision, mission and goals of this company are understood clearly, 27.2 percent are strongly agreed, 22.2 percent are agreed, 19.6 percent are neutral, 15.8 percent are disagreed and 15.2 percent are strongly disagreed that there is freedom to express my views even though they might contradict the views of their superiors.

Table-4: Effectiveness of PMS with reference to Focus in Dairy Industry of Karnataka State

SL. No	Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
1	I feel a strong sense of loyalty to the company	58 (11.6)	68 (13.6)	98 (19.6)	106 (21.2)	170 (34.0)	500 (100.0)
2	I rarely think about leaving this company to work somewhere else	57 (11.4)	87 (17.4)	93 (18.6)	112 (22.4)	151 (30.2)	500 (100.0)
3	PMS of this organization is linked with compensation	41 (8.2)	63 (12.6)	97 (19.4)	109 (21.8)	190 (38.0)	500 (100.0)
4	Promotional policy of the company is linked with PMS	62 (12.4)	84 (16.8)	100 (20.0)	117 (23.4)	137 (27.4)	500 (100.0)
5	PMS of the company identifies the training needs	39 (7.8)	63 (12.6)	105 (21.0)	123 (24.6)	170 (34.0)	500 (100.0)
6	PMS helps superiors to deal with all employees fairly	48 (9.6)	79 (15.8)	105 (21.0)	127 (25.4)	141 (28.2)	500 (100.0)
7	Job rotation measures are taken for betterment of employee	59 (11.8)	77 (15.4)	93 (18.6)	110 (22.0)	161 (32.2)	500 (100.0)
8	Recognition in this organization indicate better performance	68 (13.6)	88 (17.6)	92 (18.6)	102 (20.4)	150 (30.0)	500 (100.0)

Source: Survey data.

Table-4 presents the effectiveness of PMS with reference to focus of employees in Dairy Industry of Karnataka State. It is noticed that 34.0 percent are strongly agreed, 21.2 percent are agreed, 19.6 percent are neutral, 13.6 percent are disagreed and 11.6 percent are strongly disagreed that they feel a strong sense of loyalty to the company, 30.2 percent are strongly agreed, 22.4 percent are agreed, 18.6 percent are neutral, 17.4 percent are disagreed and 11.4 percent are strongly disagreed that they rarely think about leaving the company to work somewhere. The data shows that 38.0 percent are strongly agreed, 21.8 percent are agreed, 19.4 percent are neutral, 12.6 percent are disagreed and 8.2 percent are strongly disagreed that the PMS of this organisation is linked with compensation, 27.4 percent are strongly agreed, 23.4 percent are agreed, 20.0 percent are neutral, 16.8 percent are disagreed and 12.4 percent are strongly disagreed that their promotional policy of the company is linked with PMS. Regarding to the data it is found that 34.0 percent are strongly agreed, 24.6 percent are agreed, 21.0 percent are neutral, 12.6 percent are disagreed and 7.8 percent are strongly disagreed that the PMS of the company identifies the training needs, 28.2 percent are strongly agreed, 25.4 percent are agreed, 21.0 percent are neutral, 15.8 percent are disagreed and 9.6 percent are strongly disagreed that the PMS helps superiors to deal with all employees fairly. From the data 32.2 percent are strongly agreed, 22.0 percent are agreed, 18.6 percent are neutral, 15.4 percent are disagreed and 11.8 percent are strongly disagreed that their job rotation measures are taken for betterment of the employee, 30.0 percent are strongly agreed, 22.4 percent are agreed, 18.6 percent are neutral, 17.6 percent are disagreed and 13.6 percent are strongly disagreed that they recognition in this organization indicate better performance.

Table-5: Effectiveness of PMS with reference to Quality in Dairy Industry of Karnataka State

SL. No	Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
1	There is a need for training on PMS to improve the quality of work among employees	56 (11.2)	65 (13.0)	97 (19.4)	115 (23.0)	167 (33.4)	500 (100.0)
2	PMS improve the production and productivity	50 (10.0)	64 (12.8)	82 (16.4)	133 (26.6)	171 (34.2)	500 (100.0)
3	Managers establish plans and work objectives for quality performance	51 (10.2)	88 (17.6)	90 (18.0)	121 (24.2)	150 (30.0)	500 (100.0)
4	Goals and performance objectives are clearly specified for quality output	26 (5.2)	57 (11.4)	102 (20.4)	137 (27.4)	178 (35.6)	500 (100.0)
5	Employees are sent to training programmes for enhancing this skills and quality of work	43 (8.6)	69 (13.8)	111 (22.2)	128 (25.6)	149 (29.8)	500 (100.0)

Source: Survey data.

Table-5 presents the effectiveness of PMS with reference to quality in dairy industry of Karnataka State. Out of total respondents 33.4 percent are strongly agreed, 23.0 percent are agreed, 19.4 percent are neutral, 13.0 percent are disagreed and 11.2 percent are strongly disagreed that there is a need for training on PMS to improve the quality of work among employees, 34.2 percent are strongly agreed, 26.6 percent are agreed, 16.4 percent are neutral, 12.8 percent are disagreed and 10.0 percent are strongly disagreed that the PMS improve the production and productivity. The data shows that the respondents of 30.0 percent are strongly agreed, 24.2 percent are agreed, 18.0 percent are neutral, 17.6 percent are disagreed and 10.2 percent are strongly disagreed that their managers establish plans and work objectives for quality performance, 35.6 percent are strongly agreed, 27.4 percent are agreed, 20.4 percent are neutral, 11.4 percent are disagreed and 5.2 percent are strongly disagreed that their goals and performance objectives are clearly specified for quality output, 29.8 percent are strongly agreed, 25.6 percent are agreed, 22.2 percent are neutral, 13.8 percent are disagreed and 8.6 percent are strongly disagreed that their employees are sent to training programmes for enhancing this skills and quality of work.

Table-6: Effectiveness of PMS with reference to Cost in Dairy Industry of Karnataka State

SL. No	Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
1	My company maintains salary level that compare well to other companies	42 (8.4)	65 (13.0)	100 (20.0)	124 (24.8)	169 (33.8)	500 (100.0)
2	I receive adequate salary for my contributions / Accomplishments to the organisation	47 (9.4)	64 (12.8)	104 (20.8)	120 (24.0)	165 (33.0)	500 (100.0)
3	Process of rewarding employees is clearly understood	59 (11.8)	85 (17.0)	93 (18.6)	123 (24.6)	140 (28.0)	500 (100.0)
4	Rewards and Recognition schemes are fair and transparent	32 (6.4)	58 (11.6)	106 (21.2)	133 (26.6)	171 (34.2)	500 (100.0)
5	Company invest more on upgradation of technology	71 (14.2)	89 (17.8)	105 (21.0)	112 (22.4)	123 (24.6)	500 (100.0)

Source: Survey data.

Table-6 describes the effectiveness of PMS with reference to cost in Dairy Industry of Karnataka State. It is found that a dominated group of 33.8 percent is strongly agreed, 24.8 percent are agreed, 20.0 percent are neutral, 13.0 percent are disagreed and 8.4 percent are strongly disagreed that their company maintains salary level that compare well to other companies, 33.0 percent are strongly agreed, 24.0 percent are agreed, 20.8 percent are neutral, 12.8 percent are disagreed and 9.4 percent are strongly disagreed that they receive adequate salary for their contributions/accomplishments to the organisation. Regarding to the data 28.0 percent are strongly agreed, 24.6 percent are agreed, 18.6 percent are neutral, 17.0 percent are disagreed and 11.8 percent are strongly disagreed that the process of rewarding employees is clearly understood, 34.2 percent are strongly agreed, 26.6 percent are agreed, 21.2 percent are neutral, 11.6 percent are disagreed and 6.4 percent are strongly disagreed that the rewards and recognition schemes are fair and transparent, 24.6 percent are strongly agreed, 22.4 percent are agreed, 21.0 percent are neutral, 17.8 percent are disagreed and 14.2 percent are strongly disagreed that their company invest more on upgradation of technology.

Table-7: Effectiveness of PMS with reference to Output in Dairy Industry of Karnataka State

SL. No	Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
1	PMS helps to improve performance of service delivery in the organization	35 (7.0)	87 (17.4)	90 (18.0)	127 (25.4)	161 (32.2)	500 (100.0)
2	PMS is an opportunity to excel the performance of work	49 (9.8)	77 (15.4)	104 (20.8)	116 (23.2)	154 (30.8)	500 (100.0)
3	PMS measures one's performance of employees against the agreed target	50 (10.0)	61 (12.2)	70 (14.0)	117 (23.4)	202 (40.4)	500 (100.0)
4	My job is worthwhile and help contribute to the success of the company	41 (8.2)	70 (14.0)	100 (20.0)	131 (26.2)	158 (31.6)	500 (100.0)
5	PMS gives access to work hard and increase the productivity of the employees	76 (15.2)	81 (16.2)	103 (20.6)	108 (21.6)	132 (26.4)	500 (100.0)

Source: Survey data.

The Table-7 presents the effectiveness of PMS with reference to output in Dairy Industry of Karnataka State. According to the data a dominated group of 32.2 percent are strongly agreed, 25.4 percent are agreed, 18.0 percent are neutral, 17.4 percent are disagreed and 7.0 percent are strongly disagreed that the PMS helps to improve performance of service delivery in the organisation, 30.8 percent are strongly agreed, 23.2 percent are agreed, 20.8 percent are neutral, 15.4 percent are disagreed and 9.8 percent are strongly disagreed that the PMS is an opportunity to excel the performance of work. The data shows that 40.4 percent are strongly agreed, 23.4 percent are agreed, 14.0 percent are neutral, 12.2 percent are disagreed and 10.0 percent are strongly disagreed that the PMS measures one's performance of employees against the agreed target, 31.6 percent are strongly agreed, 26.2 percent are agreed, 20.0 percent are neutral, 14.0 percent are disagreed and 8.2 percent are strongly disagreed that their job is worthwhile and help to contribute the success of the company, 26.4 percent are strongly agreed, 21.6 percent are agreed, 20.6 percent are neutral, 16.2 percent are disagreed and 15.2 percent are strongly

disagreed that the PMS gives access to work hard and increase the productivity of the employees.

Table-8: Satisfaction levels of employees in Cooperative and Non-cooperative Dairies in Karnataka State on current PMS in the organization

SL. No	Statements	Very Unsatisfied	Unsatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Total
1	Performance planning /goal setting	28 (5.6)	39 (7.8)	85 (17.0)	166 (33.2)	182 (36.4)	500 (100.0)
2	Performance evaluation	37 (7.4)	55 (11.0)	104 (20.8)	127 (25.4)	177 (35.4)	500 (100.0)
3	Development planning	38 (7.6)	74 (14.8)	109 (21.8)	127 (25.4)	152 (30.4)	500 (100.0)
4	360-degree feedback	52 (10.4)	78 (15.6)	90 (18.0)	122 (24.4)	158 (31.6)	500 (100.0)
5	Informal feedback	29 (5.8)	57 (11.4)	101 (20.2)	136 (27.2)	177 (35.4)	500 (100.0)
6	Coaching and/or Mentoring	34 (6.8)	60 (12.0)	117 (23.4)	125 (25.0)	164 (32.8)	500 (100.0)
7	Training / Skill development	48 (9.6)	73 (14.6)	82 (16.4)	123 (24.6)	174 (34.8)	500 (100.0)
8	Leadership development	65 (13.0)	74 (14.8)	92 (18.4)	130 (26.0)	139 (27.8)	500 (100.0)
9	Rewards / Incentives	60 (12.0)	75 (15.0)	101 (20.2)	122 (24.4)	142 (28.4)	500 (100.0)
10	Discipline	46 (9.2)	73 (14.6)	99 (19.8)	114 (22.8)	168 (33.6)	500 (100.0)
11	Overall PMS	51 (10.2)	73 (14.6)	108 (21.6)	127 (25.4)	141 (28.2)	500 (100.0)

Source: Survey data.

The satisfaction levels of employees in Cooperative and Non-cooperative Dairies towards current PMS in the organization revealed that while 36.4 percent very much satisfied and 33.2 percent satisfied, 7.8 percent unsatisfied and 5.6 percent very much unsatisfied with the performance planning / goal setting. On the other hand 35.4 percent are very much satisfied, 25.4 percent satisfied, 11.0 percent unsatisfied and 7.4 percent very much unsatisfied with performance evaluation. It is observed from data 30.4 percent are very satisfied, 25.4 percent are satisfied, 21.8 percent are neutral, 14.8 percent are unsatisfied and 7.6 percent are very unsatisfied with the development planning, 31.6 percent are very satisfied, 24.4 percent are satisfied, 18.0 percent are neutral, 15.6 percent are unsatisfied and 10.4 percent are very unsatisfied with 360 degree feedback, 35.4 percent are very satisfied, 27.2 percent are satisfied, 20.2 percent are neutral, 11.4 percent are unsatisfied and 5.8 percent are very unsatisfied with informal feedback. Regarding coaching and/or mentoring the data shows 32.8 percent very much satisfied, 25.0 percent satisfied, 12.0 percent unsatisfied and 6.8 percent very much unsatisfied. With reference to training and skill development, 34.8 percent very much satisfied, 24.6 percent satisfied, but 14.6 percent unsatisfied and 9.6 percent very much unsatisfied. It is also observed 27.8 percent very much satisfied, 26.0 percent satisfied with leadership development, but 14.8 percent unsatisfied and 13.0 percent very much unsatisfied. From the data it is found that 28.4 percent very much satisfied, 24.4 percent satisfied with rewards/incentives in the organisation, but 15.0 percent unsatisfied and 12.0 percent very much unsatisfied. On other hand 33.6 percent very much satisfied and 22.8 percent satisfied with discipline, whereas 14.6 percent unsatisfied and 9.2 percent very much unsatisfied. Finally with

reference to overall performance management system in cooperative and non-cooperative dairies the data shows 28.2 percent very much satisfied and 25.4 percent satisfied, but 14.6 percent unsatisfied and 10.2 percent very much unsatisfied with this.

Table – 9: A comparative analysis of performance management system in cooperative and non-cooperative dairies in Karnataka State with reference to employee perceptions

Particulars	Category	N	Mean	Std. Dev	Std. Err	f-value	p-value
Effectiveness of PMS with reference to results and output	Co-operative	250	20.58	4.134	0.261	8.877**	0.003
	Non Co-operative	250	21.72	4.417	0.279		
	Total	500	21.15	4.311	0.193		
Effectiveness of PMS with reference to input	Co-operative	250	17.16	4.223	0.267	1.597	0.207
	Non Co-operative	250	17.61	3.686	0.233		
	Total	500	17.38	3.966	0.177		
Effectiveness of PMS with reference to time	Co-operative	250	25.64	4.493	0.284	136.528**	0.000
	Non Co-operative	250	30.29	4.409	0.279		
	Total	500	27.97	5.019	0.224		
Effectiveness of PMS with reference to focus	Co-operative	250	27.91	3.908	0.247	0.045	0.832
	Non Co-operative	250	27.98	4.084	0.258		
	Total	500	27.95	3.993	0.179		
Effectiveness of PMS with reference to quality	Co-operative	250	17.85	2.873	0.182	0.397	0.529
	Non Co-operative	250	18.02	3.220	0.204		
	Total	500	17.94	3.050	0.136		
Effectiveness of PMS with reference to cost	Co-operative	250	17.41	3.443	0.218	1.155	0.283
	Non Co-operative	250	17.73	3.124	0.198		
	Total	500	17.57	3.288	0.147		
Effectiveness of PMS with reference to output	Co-operative	250	17.48	2.998	2.998	1.980	0.160
	Non Co-operative	250	17.86	2.913	2.913		
	Total	500	17.67	2.959	2.959		
Satisfaction levels towards current PMS	Co-operative	250	38.18	4.757	0.301	44.248**	0.000
	Non Co-operative	250	40.86	4.208	0.266		
	Total	500	39.52	4.682	0.209		
Satisfaction levels towards current PMS	Co-operative	250	38.18	4.757	0.301	44.248**	0.000
	Non Co-operative	250	40.86	4.208	0.266		
	Total	500	39.52	4.682	0.209		

Source: Survey data.

A comparative analysis on effectiveness of performance management system in cooperative and non-cooperative dairies with reference to results the data reveals that the average score of 21.72 perceived by the employees of Non-Cooperative dairies found higher than the average score of 20.58 perceived by the employees of Cooperative dairies and their respective standard deviations are 4.417 and 4.134. With these mean and standard deviation differences the calculated f-value 8.877 is significant at 1% level because the p-value is 0.003. This indicates that there is a significant difference between the perceptions of the employees in cooperative and non-cooperative dairies towards effectiveness of PMS with reference to results and output of study units, where non-cooperative dairy employees are more positive. The effectiveness of PMS with reference to input in cooperative and non-cooperative dairies it is found that the average score of 17.61 perceived by employees in Non-Cooperative dairy found higher than the average score of 17.16 perceived by employees in Cooperative dairy and their respective standard deviations are 3.686 and 4.223. With these mean and standard deviation differences the calculated f-value 1.597 is not significant at any level because the p-value is 0.207. This indicates that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of the employees in

cooperative and non-cooperative dairies towards effectiveness of PMS with reference to input of study organisations. Regarding the effectiveness of PMS with reference to time in cooperative and non-cooperative dairies, the average perceived score of 30.29 by Non-Cooperative dairy employees found higher than the average score of 25.64 perceived by Cooperative dairy and their respective standard deviations are 4.409 and 4.493. With these mean and standard deviation differences the calculated f-value 136.528 is significant at 1% level because the p-value is 0.000. This indicates that there is a significant difference between the perceptions of the employees in cooperative and non-cooperative dairies towards effectiveness of PMS with reference to time in the study units, where the non-cooperative dairy employees are more positive in this regard than their counterpart cooperative dairy employees. The effectiveness of PMS with reference to focus of cooperative and non-cooperative dairies the average score of 27.98 perceived by the employees of Non-Cooperative dairy found higher than the average score of 27.91 perceived by the employees of Cooperative dairy and their standard deviations are 4.084 and 3.908 respectively. According to the difference in the mean and standard deviation values the calculated f-value 0.045 is not significant at any level because the p-value is 0.832. This infers that there is no significant difference in the perceptions of the employees working in cooperative and non-cooperative dairies toward effectiveness of PMS with reference to the focus of study units.

The effectiveness of PMS with reference to quality of products in cooperative and non-cooperative dairies reveals that the average score of 18.02 perceived by the employees of Non-Cooperative dairy found higher than the average score of 17.85 perceived by the employees of Cooperative dairy and their respective standard deviations are 3.220 and 2.873. With these mean and standard deviation differences the calculated f-value 0.397 found no significant because the p-value is 0.529. This shows that there is no significant difference in the perceptions of employees in cooperative and non-cooperative dairies towards effectiveness of PMS with reference to quality of products in the study units. The effectiveness of PMS with reference to cost of products in cooperative and non-cooperative dairies the data reveals that the average score of 17.73 perceived by the employees of Non-Cooperative dairy found higher than the average score of 17.41 perceived by the employees of Cooperative dairy and their respective standard deviations are 3.124 and 3.443. With these mean and standard deviation differences the calculated f-value 1.155 is not significant because the p-value is 0.283. This indicates that there is no significant difference found between the perceptions of cooperative and non-cooperative dairy employees toward effectiveness of PMS with reference to cost of products in the study units. Regarding the effectiveness of PMS with reference to output in cooperative and non-cooperative dairies the average score of 17.86 perceived by the employees of Non-Cooperative dairy found higher than the average score of 17.48 perceived by the employees of Cooperative dairy and their standard deviations are 2.913 and 2.998 respectively. With these mean and standard deviation differences the calculated f-value 1.980 indicates not significant because the p-value is 0.160. This infers that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of the employees working in cooperative and non-cooperative dairies toward effectiveness of PMS with reference to output of study units. With reference to satisfaction levels of employees towards current PMS in cooperative and non-cooperative

dairies it is observed that the average score of 40.86 perceived by the employees of Non-Cooperative dairy found higher than the average score of 38.18 perceived by the employees of Cooperative dairy and their respective standard deviations are 4.208 and 4.757. With these mean and standard deviation differences the calculated f-value 44.248 indicates significant at 1% level because the p-value is 0.000. This infers that there is a significant difference in the perceptions of cooperative and non-cooperative dairy employees where non-cooperative dairy employees are more satisfaction towards current PMS in their organisation.

Conclusion

A comparative analysis on effectiveness of performance management system in cooperative and non-cooperative dairies revealed that there is a significant difference found between cooperative and non-cooperative dairies towards effectiveness of PMS with reference to results and output, where non-cooperative dairy are found better than cooperative dairies. With reference to input, focus, quality and output of PMS in cooperative and non-cooperative dairies shows that there is no significant difference. Whereas, with reference to time of PMS in cooperative and non-cooperative dairies there is a significant difference found between these two dairy industries, where the non-cooperative dairy employees are more positive in this regard than their counterpart cooperative dairy employees. Hence, the satisfaction levels of employees towards current PMS in cooperative and non-cooperative dairies indicate significant because the Non-Cooperative dairy employees found higher satisfaction than the employees of Cooperative dairy.

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